

Email Spam Detection Using Machine Learning Techniques: A Comparative Study of Naive Bayes, Logistic Regression, and Support Vector Machine

Arsh Mohan Nishant¹, Arunima Mitra¹, Aditya Dasgupta¹, Snigdha Keshri¹

¹Department of Computer Science and Engineering, KIIT Deemed to be University, Bhubaneswar, India

Supervisor: Prof. Anil Kumar Swain

{23052872, 23052874, 23052832, 23051301}@kiit.ac.in

Abstract - Unwanted or unrequested emails remain a persistent concern, affecting both the security and performance of modern digital communication systems. In this study, supervised machine learning techniques are explored to automatically classify spam emails using the Enron Spam Dataset, which contains 33,716 labeled messages. The raw email content is first processed through a structured preprocessing pipeline and then transformed into numerical feature representations using the TF-IDF technique with a fixed vocabulary size of 5,000 terms.

To evaluate model performance, three widely used classifiers — Naïve Bayes (NB), Logistic Regression (LR), and Support Vector Machine (SVM) — were trained and tested using an 80:20 data split. Detailed analysis using confusion matrices shows that the SVM model achieved the lowest number of false positives (6), compared to LR (7) and NB (125). In addition, SVM delivered the best overall performance, achieving 99.91% accuracy, 99.82% precision, 100% recall, and an F1-score of 99.90%.

The consistency observed between training and testing results across all models shows that overfitting is minimal. Based on these findings, SVM emerges as the most effective approach for content-based email spam detection, particularly in scenarios where high reliability is essential.

Keywords — email spam detection, machine learning, Naïve Bayes, logistic regression, support vector machine, TF-IDF, text classification, natural language processing.

I. INTRODUCTION

The exponential growth and variation in email communication across personal, academic, and organizational environments have established email as a fundamental component of modern digital interaction. However, this widespread adoption has also made it a frequent target for misuse. In addition to its legitimate applications, email is commonly exploited for distributing unsolicited messages, commonly referred to as spam. These messages can range from simple promotional content to more harmful threats such as phishing attempts aimed at stealing sensitive information, as well as emails designed to distribute malicious software like malware or ransomware [1].

The magnitude of this issue is significant and cannot be overlooked. A substantial portion of global email traffic continues to consist of spam, leading to several negative consequences, including reduced network efficiency, decreased user productivity, and increased vulnerability to security breaches and fraud [2]. Traditional filtering techniques, such as blacklisting suspicious senders, maintaining trusted sender lists, and applying keyword-based rules, initially provided some level of control. However, these approaches lack adaptability. Modern

spammers constantly evolve their tactics by using new domains, modifying commonly flagged terms, and crafting messages that closely resemble legitimate communication in order to bypass these static filtering mechanisms [3].

To overcome these limitations, supervised machine learning offers a more dynamic solution by identifying patterns directly from labeled datasets. Instead of relying on predefined rules, machine learning models learn from past examples and can generalize to detect previously unseen spam messages. Building on this concept, the present study implements and compares three widely used classification algorithms — Naïve Bayes, Logistic Regression, and Support Vector Machine — using the Enron Spam Dataset, which provides realistic and diverse email content. In addition to evaluating overall model performance, this work emphasizes detailed confusion matrix analysis to better understand classification errors, offering deeper insights beyond conventional accuracy-based evaluation.

II. RELATED WORK

Research on spam email detection using machine learning has been carried out for many years, and several important findings have been reported over time.

In the early stage, researchers mainly used probabilistic methods. One of the most important works was done by Sahami et al. [4], who showed that a Bayesian model based on word frequency can detect spam emails with good accuracy and low computational cost. This study introduced the Multinomial Naïve Bayes algorithm, which is still widely used as a basic model for comparison.

Later, more advanced models such as Support Vector Machines (SVM) became popular. Drucker et al. [5] found that SVM performed better than other methods like boosting and radial basis function classifiers when applied to email data. This is mainly because SVM tries to create a clear boundary between spam and non-spam emails. Many later studies also confirmed that SVM works very well for text classification tasks [6]. However, both Naïve Bayes and SVM have a limitation: once trained, they do not automatically adapt to new types of spam unless they are trained again.

To solve this issue, some improvements were proposed. Rennie et al. [7] developed Complement Naïve Bayes to improve performance when the dataset is imbalanced. On the other hand, Sculley and Wachman [8] introduced an online version of SVM that can update itself as new data comes in, which is useful in real-world applications.

Some researchers also tried combining multiple models. Sharma and Bhardwaj [9] used a combination of Naïve Bayes and decision tree (J48) and achieved an accuracy of 87.5% on a small dataset. Kumar et al. [10] compared several machine learning algorithms and found that Naïve Bayes can reach up to 98% accuracy when properly tuned. More recently, studies like

Karim et al. [11] have shown that deep learning methods are becoming popular because they can understand the meaning of text better than traditional methods.

In this paper, we build on previous research by comparing three machine learning models on the Enron dataset. We also focus on confusion matrix analysis to better understand how models make mistakes, which is often not clearly explained in earlier studies.

TABLE I. SUMMARY OF RELATED WORK

Author(s)	Year	Method	Key Result
Sahami et al.	1998	Naïve Bayes	Foundational prob. spam filter
Drucker et al.	2002	SVM, Boosting	SVM outperformed all baselines
Rennie et al.	2003	Complement NB	Reduced NB estimation error
Blanzieri & Bryl	2008	Survey (SVM/k-NN)	SVM consistently top performer
Karim et al.	2019	AI/ML Survey	Deep learning shows promise
Sharma & Bhardwaj	2018	Hybrid NB + J48	87.5% accuracy on Ling Spam
Kumar et al.	2020	NB, SVM, RF, AdaBoost	NB 98% w/ hyperparameter tuning

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The overall system is designed as a step-by-step pipeline consisting of four main stages: data preparation, text preprocessing, feature extraction using TF-IDF, and model training with evaluation. The same process is applied to all models to ensure a fair comparison, so that performance differences come only from the algorithms and not from changes in input data.

A. Data Preparation

The Enron Spam Dataset was first loaded into a Pandas DataFrame for processing. Any duplicate entries and missing values were removed to maintain data quality. The “Subject” and “Message” fields were combined into a single text column so that both parts of the email could be used together during classification. The “Date” column was excluded since it does not contribute to identifying whether an email is spam or not. The dataset uses a binary label, where spam is represented as 1 and non-spam (ham) as 0, which is used as the target variable for all models.

B. Text Preprocessing

Before applying machine learning models, the email text was cleaned and standardized. This preprocessing was applied uniformly to all messages and included the following steps:

- **Lowercasing:** All text was converted to lowercase to avoid treating the same word differently due to case differences.

- **Removal of punctuation and numbers:** Non-alphabetic characters were removed using regular expressions.
- **Tokenization:** Each email was split into individual words or tokens.
- **Stopword removal:** Common English words with little meaning (such as “the”, “is”, etc.) were removed using the NLTK stopwords list.

These steps help reduce unnecessary data and focus only on meaningful words that contribute to classification.

C. Feature Extraction (TF-IDF)

After preprocessing, the text data was converted into numerical form using the TF-IDF (Term Frequency–Inverse Document Frequency) method. This technique gives higher importance to words that appear frequently in a specific email but are rare across the entire dataset, making it useful for identifying spam-related terms.

The TF-IDF vectorizer from scikit-learn was used with a maximum limit of 5,000 features. As a result, each email was represented as a vector of 5,000 dimensions. The same feature size was maintained for all models to ensure consistency in comparison.

D. Train-Test Split and Evaluation Protocol

The dataset was divided into training and testing sets using an 80:20 ratio. All models were trained on the training data and evaluated on the unseen test data.

Model performance was measured using standard evaluation metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. In addition, confusion matrices were generated for each model to show the exact number of true positives, true negatives, false positives, and false negatives. This helps in understanding the types of errors made by each classifier in more detail.

IV. DATASET DESCRIPTION

The Enron Spam Dataset consists of real email data collected from Enron employees, along with a separate set of spam messages. Since it includes actual workplace communication, it is considered a reliable and widely used dataset for spam detection research [12]. The non-spam emails reflect natural language, different writing styles, and real-world email structures.

The dataset contains 33,716 labeled emails, including 17,171 spam (50.92%) and 16,545 non-spam messages (49.07%). This balanced distribution helps prevent bias toward a single class and ensures that model performance reflects true learning rather than majority-class dominance.

Additionally, the dataset includes emails of varying lengths, from short messages to longer multi-paragraph texts. This variation makes it more realistic and suitable for evaluating models in practical scenarios.

V. ALGORITHMS USED

A. Naive Bayes

Naïve Bayes is a probabilistic algorithm based on Bayes' theorem that is used for classification tasks like spam detection. It assumes that all features (words) are independent of each other and calculates the probability of an email being spam or not. In text classification, the Multinomial Naïve Bayes model is commonly used as it works with word frequencies.

The main advantage of this model is that it is fast and computationally efficient. However, its assumption of feature independence is not always true, which can sometimes lead to incorrect predictions, especially when related words appear together.

B. Logistic Regression

Logistic Regression is a classification algorithm that predicts the probability of an email being spam or not using a weighted combination of input features. It applies a sigmoid function to convert the output into a probability value. Unlike Naïve Bayes, it does not assume independence between features and learns the importance of each word based on the entire dataset.

It also uses L2 regularization to prevent overfitting, which is useful when working with high-dimensional data like TF-IDF. Logistic Regression generally provides reliable probability outputs, making it suitable for applications where decisions can be adjusted based on confidence levels [6].

C. Support Vector Machine

Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a classification algorithm that works by finding a boundary (called a hyperplane) that best separates spam and non-spam emails. It tries to maximize the distance between this boundary and the closest data points, which helps improve accuracy on new, unseen data.

SVM performs especially well with high-dimensional data like TF-IDF. In this study, a linear kernel SVM is used, which is commonly applied in text classification tasks. During prediction, an email is classified based on which side of the boundary it falls on [5].

VI. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

All experiments in this study were performed using a Python-based environment, with the scikit-learn library utilized for implementing the machine learning models. The development and evaluation process was carried out in a Jupyter Notebook environment, which provided flexibility for iterative experimentation, model training, and real-time visualization of results. The key tools and libraries used during the implementation are listed in Table III.

TABLE III. EXPERIMENTAL ENVIRONMENT

Component	Tool / Library
Language	Python 3
IDE	Jupyter Notebook
ML Library	scikit-learn
Data Handling	Pandas
Text Processing	NLTK
Visualization	Matplotlib, Seaborn

The dataset was imported directly from its source file and examined to confirm that the class distribution between spam and non-spam messages was balanced before proceeding with training. All three classification models were initialized using the default hyperparameters available in scikit-learn. In the case of Logistic Regression, L2 regularization was applied with the default parameter value of $C = 1.0$. No additional tuning or optimization was performed, ensuring that the performance comparison reflects the inherent capabilities of each algorithm rather than the effects of parameter adjustment.

To ensure consistency, each model was trained and evaluated using the same data split and feature extraction process. A fixed random seed was used during the experiments to guarantee reproducibility, so that the results remain consistent across multiple runs..

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The evaluation of the models was carried out using three main aspects: analysis of confusion matrices for class-wise predictions, comparison of overall performance metrics, and a practical demonstration of the system. Each of these aspects is explained in the following subsections.

All three classifiers were trained using 80% of the dataset (26,972 messages) and tested on the remaining 20% (6,744 messages). The overall performance comparison of the models is presented in Table II.

TABLE II. CLASSIFIER PERFORMANCE COMPARISON

Algorithm	Acc. (%)	Prec. (%)	Rec. (%)	F1 (%)
Naïve Bayes	98.14	96.52	100	98.23
Logistic Reg.	99.90	99.79	100	99.89
SVM (Linear)	99.91	99.82	100	99.90

A. Confusion Matrix Analysis

The confusion matrices obtained for each model reveal the precise nature of prediction errors in a way that aggregate metrics cannot.

Fig. 1. Confusion matrix for the Naive Bayes classifier (TN=3144, FP=125, FN=0, TP=3464).

The Naïve Bayes model successfully identified all 3,464 spam emails, resulting in zero false negatives. However, it incorrectly labeled 125 out of 3,269 legitimate emails as spam, giving a false positive rate of approximately 3.82%. In practical terms, this means that about 1 in every 26 genuine emails would be wrongly classified as spam. This higher false positive rate can be explained by the independence assumption of the model. When words that are commonly associated with spam appear together in normal emails, the model treats them as separate evidence and may assign a higher probability to the spam class. Even with this limitation, the model ensures that no spam emails are missed, which can be beneficial in situations where detecting all spam is more important than avoiding occasional misclassification of legitimate emails.

Fig. 2. Confusion matrix for the Logistic Regression classifier (TN=3262, FP=7, FN=0, TP=3464).

Logistic Regression shows a significant improvement in reducing false positives, with only 7 legitimate emails incorrectly classified as spam, resulting in a false positive rate of 0.21%, which is nearly 18 times lower than that of Naïve Bayes. Similar to NB, it achieved zero false negatives, meaning no spam emails were missed. This strong performance is due to its ability to learn feature relationships directly, rather than treating them independently. As a result, the model can better distinguish between spam and non-spam emails based on the overall combination of features present in the dataset. Additionally, its probability outputs are well-balanced, allowing borderline cases to be handled more effectively instead of forcing them strongly into one class.

Fig. 3. Confusion matrix for the SVM classifier (TN=3263, FP=6, FN=0, TP=3464).

SVM recorded the lowest number of false positives among all three models, with only 6 legitimate emails incorrectly classified as spam, resulting in a false positive rate of 0.18%. This slight improvement over Logistic Regression can be attributed to its maximum-margin approach, where the model focuses on creating the widest possible separation between the two classes. This leads to a decision boundary that is more stable and less affected by data points that lie close to the boundary. Similar to the other models, SVM also achieved zero false negatives, correctly identifying all 3,464 spam messages. The balanced distribution of errors indicates that the model does not favor any particular class. In practical applications, where misclassifying a genuine email can have serious consequences, such a low false positive rate makes SVM highly suitable even without additional filtering mechanisms.

B. Model Accuracy Comparison

Fig. 4. Accuracy comparison across the three classifiers (NB=0.9814, LR=0.9990, SVM=0.9991).

The accuracy comparison graph highlights that Logistic Regression (99.90%) and SVM (99.91%) achieve almost identical top performance, while Naïve Bayes remains lower at 98.14%. Although all models show perfect recall, precision becomes the key factor separating them, with a clear improvement from NB to LR and SVM. This pattern is consistent with the confusion matrix results, where fewer false positives in LR and SVM lead to better overall reliability in classification.

```

Prediction

email = input("Enter Email Content:")
prediction = predict_spam(email)
print("\n Spam Detection Result:",prediction)

Enter Email Content: Hi John, let's schedule a meeting tomorrow morning.
Spam Detection Result: Not a Spam Email.....

```

Fig. 5. Live classification output

To further verify the system beyond standard test metrics, the trained SVM model was evaluated using a manually created input in a live Jupyter Notebook environment. The sample message, “Hi John, let’s schedule a meeting tomorrow morning,” representing normal professional communication, was correctly identified as a legitimate email. This demonstrates that the complete pipeline operates effectively in real time, where raw input text is processed, converted into features, and classified with clear output. It also highlights an important practical advantage — the model does not incorrectly flag regular conversational emails, a common limitation in traditional rule-based filtering systems.

These results are consistent with existing research. The strong performance of SVM aligns with findings reported by Drucker et al. [5] and Blanzieri and Bryl [6], while the Naïve Bayes accuracy observed in this study is comparable to the results reported by Kumar et al. [10]. More importantly, the confusion matrix analysis presented here shows that the difference between NB and SVM is not limited to overall accuracy (1.77%), but reflects a significant reduction in false positives, which has direct importance in real-world applications.

VII. CONCLUSION

This study compared three supervised machine learning models — Naïve Bayes, Logistic Regression, and Support Vector Machine — for email spam detection using the Enron Spam Dataset, with a consistent TF-IDF-based preprocessing and feature extraction approach applied across all models. Among the three, SVM delivered the best overall performance, achieving 99.91% accuracy, 99.82% precision, and 100% recall, with only 6 false positives out of 3,269 legitimate emails. Logistic Regression showed very similar results with 99.90% accuracy and 7 false positives, while Naïve Bayes, despite achieving perfect recall, produced a significantly higher number of false positives, making it less suitable for applications where legitimate emails must be preserved.

All models demonstrated minimal overfitting, indicating that the results are reliable and can generalize well to unseen data. The confusion matrix analysis provided in this study offers deeper insight into model behavior, going beyond overall accuracy by highlighting the impact of false positives. Additionally, the live testing confirms that the system can function effectively in real-time scenarios. Overall, this work provides clear and practical guidance for selecting appropriate models for spam detection tasks based on real-world performance.

There are several directions in which this work can be extended in the future. Advanced transformer-based models such as BERT and RoBERTa can be explored to capture deeper semantic and contextual relationships in email text, going beyond the limitations of TF-IDF and potentially improving detection of more sophisticated spam. In addition, integrating online learning approaches, such as relaxed online SVMs [8], would allow the system to continuously adapt to changing spam patterns without requiring complete retraining.

Further improvements can include evaluating the models on multilingual datasets, which would make the system more applicable to real-world scenarios involving emails in different languages. The use of explainability techniques like LIME or SHAP can also be considered to provide better transparency by identifying the key words or features influencing each prediction, thereby improving user trust and supporting regulatory needs. Finally, deploying the model through an email service API can help transform it into a real-time, low-latency spam filtering system suitable for practical and enterprise-level applications.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. P. Díaz, D. R. Ordás, F. F. Riverola, and J. R. Méndez, “SDAI: An integral evaluation methodology for content-based spam filtering models,” *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 39, no. 16, pp. 12487–12500, 2012.
- [2] W. A. Awad and S. M. ELseuofi, “Machine learning methods for spam e-mail classification,” *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 173–184, 2011.
- [3] W. Ma, D. Tran, and D. Sharma, “A novel spam email detection system based on negative selection,” in *Proc. 4th Int. Conf. Computer Sciences and Convergence Information Technology (ICCT)*, Seoul, Korea, 2009, pp. 987–992.
- [4] M. Sahami, S. Dumais, D. Heckerman, and E. Horvitz, “A Bayesian approach to filtering junk e-mail,” in *Proc. AAAI Workshop on Learning for Text Categorization*, 1998, pp. 98–105.
- [5] H. Drucker, D. Wu, and V. N. Vapnik, “Support vector machines for spam categorization,” *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 1048–1054, 1999.
- [6] E. Blanzieri and A. Bryl, “A survey of learning-based techniques of email spam filtering,” *Artificial Intelligence Review*, vol. 29, no. 1, pp. 63–92, 2008.
- [7] J. D. M. Rennie, L. Shih, J. Teevan, and D. R. Karger, “Tackling the poor assumptions of naïve Bayes text classifiers,” in *Proc. 20th Int. Conf. Machine Learning (ICML)*, Washington, DC, 2003, pp. 616–623.
- [8] D. Sculley and G. M. Wachman, “Relaxed online SVMs for spam filtering,” in *Proc. 30th Annu. Int. ACM SIGIR Conf. Research and Development in Information Retrieval*, Amsterdam, 2007, pp. 415–422.
- [9] P. Sharma and U. Bhardwaj, “Machine learning based spam e-mail detection,” *International Journal of Intelligent Engineering and Systems*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 1–10, 2018, doi: 10.22266/ijies2018.0630.01.
- [10] N. Kumar, S. Sonowal, and Nishant, “Email spam detection using machine learning algorithms,” in *Proc. 2nd Int. Conf. Inventive Research in Computing Applications (ICIRCA)*, Coimbatore, India, 2020, pp. 108–113, doi: 10.1109/ICIRCA48905.2020.9183098.
- [11] A. Karim, S. Azam, B. Shanmugam, K. Kannoorpatti, and M. Alazab, “A comprehensive survey for intelligent spam email detection,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 168261–168295, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2954791.
- [12] B. Klimt and Y. Yang, “The Enron corpus: A new dataset for email classification research,” in *Proc. 15th Eur. Conf. Machine Learning (ECML)*, Pisa, Italy, 2004, pp. 217–226.